

TOURISM: BASIC CONCEPTS, OBJECTIVES AND OBJECTIVES. TOURIST TRAVEL DESTINATIONS

Nurmatova Zakhro

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Language.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7732493>

ABSTRACT

In this article given Information about tourism goals, basic concepts, objectives and objectives, tourist travel destinations.

Key words: Every tourist, trip or tourist trip, special shopping, government of the country.

Introduction

There are many definitions of tourist, which reflect the direction of the regulatory act and the specific economic interests of the state by being relevant. In fact, experts have been working on this definition for more than 50 years. The first definitions of a tourist were compiled in 1937 by the League of Nations Special Committee of Experts on Statistics. It is recommended to consider a tourist as a person with the following characteristics: movement, temporary stay in a certain place, lack of connection with work and income. D. Frchtling analyzed the definitions of the term "tourist" in detail. As a result, he identified four main criteria used in all formulations of the concept of "tourist": travel purpose; type of vehicle used; length of stay; distance covered. Generally, the first two criteria are recognized as unimportant for practical comparative definitions, and all attention is focused on the last two. Length of stay is a key component of the UN definition, according to which a tourist must stay in the destination for more than 24 hours but less than 12 months. Some definitions are primarily based on distance criteria. For example, the US National Tourism Evaluation Commission defines a tourist as "a person who travels more than 50 miles (one way) from his home for business, pleasure, personal or other purposes other than business travel." The US Census Bureau uses the same definition and sets the minimum distance at 100 miles. In various studies, E. Cohen has identified six main dimensions by meaningfully describing the term "tourist": stability, voluntariness, direction, distance, frequency and purpose. He himself turned the tourist into a temporary traveller, who willingly traveled for the pleasure of novelty and gained experience during a relatively long journey that included a return to the starting point. This definition has its drawbacks - it has no time and space boundaries. In order to solve the set tasks, at the UN International Conference on Tourism and Travel held in Rome in 1963, the issues of tourist definitions were considered and "visitors", "tourists" (overnight visitors) and "attention attractions" (non-overnight guests). The following definition of the concept "tourist": A person who comes to the country for treatment, entertainment, education, recreation, religion, sports, leisure time, does not live permanently and does not engage in paid professional activities, for family or business reasons.

Results

In addition, under visitor means any person who travels for a period of not more than 12 consecutive months to a place outside the usual environment, the main purpose of which is

not to engage in an activity paid from a source in the place of visit. The UN conference recommended the use of this definition for statistical purposes. Visitors include tourists and tourists. The concept of "tourist" adopted by international organizations differs from the concept of "excursionist": a tourist spends more than one day outside his permanent place of residence, and a person who sees an attraction - less than one day. For example, according to the UNWTO, a tourist is a temporary visitor, that is, a person who is in a country other than the place of residence for any purpose other than performing paid activities. The main goals are study, treatment, transit. Thus, a tourist is a person who has been away from the place of permanent residence for at least 24 hours and no more than one year. According to the recommendations of the UNWTO, the category of tourists also includes crew members of foreign aircraft and ships who spend at least one night in the accommodation facilities of the host country. The category of excursionists includes passengers of sea and river cruises living on board, crew members of foreign aircraft and sea vessels who are temporarily in the country for no more than one day, as well as one-day visitors in transit. .

Discussion

UNWTO traveler classification. Applying these definitions to domestic tourism, a tourist must be considered a consumer of a tour, tourist product or tourist service - regardless of nationality, nationality, gender, language or religion, wherever he is at least in this territory, a temporary visitor in a settlement, region or country. 24 hours during a calendar year, but not exceeding 6 months, or who are away from their home country and spend at least one night in collective or individual accommodation, for pleasure or lim, medical, commercial purposes and temporary residence, not engaged in activities paid from local sources. It is also necessary to identify categories of travelers who are not considered tourists and, accordingly, are not taken into account by statistics. This includes: persons traveling in their usual place of residence; migrants - citizens who have changed their place of permanent residence or left their place of permanent residence for more than a year; persons without a permanent place of residence - nomads, homeless people; refugees and displaced persons; persons traveling to engage in paid activities at the place of temporary residence;

guest workers and residents of border regions - frontals;

representatives of diplomatic structures;

military personnel traveling for military service, as well as their family members;

illegal immigrants;

repatriated prisoners from certain countries or regions;

sleeping in carriages, participants of group trips on tourist trains;

members of group bus tours who spend the night in their cabins;

crew members of ships and trains sleeping in cabins or carriages;

flight crew members who spend the night at the destination.

Thus, the following criteria can be distinguished that distinguish tourists from other groups of travelers:

trips are made outside the place of permanent residence;

the time of stay in the tourist destination is from 24 hours to one year (half a year);

the destination component of the trip is clearly defined;

that it is not possible to engage in activities paid from a local source at the place of temporary residence. According to the types of tourism, tourists are divided into two types: international and domestic. An international tourist is a person who travels to a country other than his

usual place of residence and is outside the main environment of this person, visiting for a period of not more than 12 months, the main purpose of which is not to engage in paid activities from sources. staying at least one night in collective or private accommodation facilities in the place of visit and the country of visit. Domestic tourist. The situation with its definition is more complicated. To date, UNWTO experts do not have a single point of view on this issue. Some countries try to give their own definition of domestic tourist. Thus, UNWTO's National Tourism Resources Commission defines a domestic tourist as a person who leaves their place of permanent residence to visit a place at least 50 miles (80.5 km) from their place of residence. This trip can have professional, recreational, personal and other purposes, except for individual daily trips to the workplace. A local tourist does not need to stay at their destination for more than 24 hours, which means they can stay overnight at their destination or return home the same day. N.I. Kabushkin and A.P. Durovich gives the following definition: "Domestic tourist is a person who lives permanently in the country, travels to a certain place in his country, outside the usual environment of this person, for a period of no more than 12 months, this is the main purpose. prohibits activities paid from the source in the visited place and at least one night in collective or private residential buildings in the visited place All tourists can be classified according to the following criteria: depending on their activity or lifestyle. According to tradition, six groups are distinguished among tourists according to their activity during vacation sea. A typical vacationer who prefers a passive vacation, peace and comfort in sea resorts; avoids noise, but prefers communication with nice people. Type F (u. Ferme und Flirtorientierter Eriebnisur Lauber - a vacationer who prefers to travel long distances and flirt). This type is characterized by a desire for a constant change of faces, events, impressions. He spends his vacation only where something is happening, because "roasting" on the beach with his family or alone does not suit him. The credo of such a tourist is the change of society, pleasure, impressions. W-1 type (u. Wald und wanderorientiert - one who likes forest walks and walks). A vacationer who prefers outdoor walks, hiking, etc. His reputation is exercise in the fresh air regardless of the weather. On vacation, he tries to keep in good physical shape, but does not play professional sports. Type W-2 is more of an athlete than an amateur. Long and large, withstands extreme loads. When choosing an excursion, the criteria for the conditions for the work you love prevail. Selection criteria such as "landscape, culture, history" are secondary (for example, amateur pilot, passionate climber, etc.). Type A (u. Abentener - adventurer). Adventure lover. Danger, new sensations, trying one's strength in unexpected situations, danger - this determines the choice of a travel destination for this tourist. Type B (u. Bildung und Besichtigung - education and excursion). Curious tourists are divided into three subgroups:

"experts" who "collect" the visited attractions;

"emotional" lovers of culture and nature;

"experts" who deepen their knowledge in certain areas of culture, history, art, etc.

Conclusion

Tourism must have a purpose. It is impossible to have tourism without a purpose. Its most common type is recreation and health. A person's health is above all else, and he travels for this purpose. The rational use of natural resources for tourism purposes is of great importance. The role of social tourism is also special. And politics defines the basis of tourism objectives. Where there is peace, there is tourism. Basic phrases, Tourism purpose, Rest, Health, Social tourism, Politics

References:

- 1.Arefiev V.E. Access to tourism. Barnaul: Altai State University, 2002.
- 2.Birzhakov MB. Access to tourism. M.; SPb.: Nevsky Foundation; Gerda, 2007.
- 3.Dmitrienko Yu.V., Karmashkova NV, Chernova TV. Basics of tourism business. Khabarovsk: FVGUPS, 2003.
- 4.Guliev N.A., Kulagina E.V. Admission to the specialty: Tourism. Omsk: OGIS, 2002.

